

Hemin-collodion Membrane Electrode for Measurement of Anion Activity in Electrolytic Solutions. Part II. Br⁻, I⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, and IO₃⁻ Activities

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Cl⁻ ion in the film membrane of hemin-collodion has been exchanged by Br⁻, I⁻, IO₃⁻, NO₃⁻, or SO₄²⁻ ion by keeping in contact with neutral aqueous solution of the respective salt for about 72 to 125 hours, the time for conditioning varying with the nature of the ion. The film membranes of various salts of hematin have been prepared and used in the determination of anion activities of aqueous solutions of the respective salts at pH 6.7 by measuring membrane potentials at molarity ratio 2 at 25°. The valid range of concentration in each case, for which the Nernst equation is applicable, has been determined.

In extension of our previous work¹, we have attempted to ascertain the utilities of bromide, iodide, nitrate, sulphate, and iodate of hematin, obtained by exchange of chloride ion in hemin-collodion membrane electrode, in the determination of the anion activities of neutral aqueous solutions of various corresponding salts and the molarity ratio as well as the range of concentration for which the Nernst equation could be applied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hemin-collodion film membranes of different thickness between 0.20 mm and 0.44 mm were prepared by the method described previously¹. The prepared films were soaked first in water for 24 hr. to swell and then in 1*N* aqueous solution of the respective electrolyte for 72 hours to exchange Cl⁻ for the respective anion. In the case of hematin hydroiodide film membrane, soaking in 1*N*-KI was continued for 5 days for conditioning and then it was soaked in CO₂-free water for 2 hr. Only the film membranes having zero or negligible asymmetric potential were used in the experiments. The complete exchange condition was judged from the constant value of the membrane potential in the case of aqueous solutions (0.0015 and 0.0030*M*) of the same salt on the two sides. Thus the anion activities of KBr, NaBr, NH₄Br, KNO₃, NH₄NO₃, NH₄I, KI, KIO₃, and K₂SO₄ solutions were determined at various concentration ranges at molarity ratio 2 at 25°. The film membrane, used in each of the experiments, was of different thickness, 0.20 mm to 0.44 mm. Reproducibility of the observed membrane potential was checked by repeated change of solutions. The equilibrium was established within 15 minutes and membrane potential readings remained constant for more than ½ hr.

The activity coefficients of Br⁻, I⁻, SO₄²⁻, and IO₃⁻ ions were obtained by plotting the values recorded by Conway² and the same for the NO₃⁻ ions by Lewis and Randall³. The experimental values of the membrane potential were compared with those calculated from the Nernst equation at 25° (Table I).

$$E = \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{a_2}{a_1}$$

1. Pandit, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 917.

2. "Electro-Chemical Data".

3. "Thermodynamics and Free Energy of Chemical Substances".

TABLE

Membrane potentials of hemin-collodion films of different thickness in diff. electrolyte solutions of diff. conc. with molarity ratio 2 at 25°.

1. Electrolyte 2. Film thickness	Molarity.		Anion activity.		Mem. potentials(mv).	
	Inside.	Outside.	Inside.	Outside.	Obs.	Calc.
1. KBr 2. 0.31 mm	0.0031	0.0015	0.00296	0.00146	18.00	18.10
	0.0062	0.0031	0.00583	0.00296	17.50	17.37
	0.0125	0.0062	0.01143	0.00583	17.00	17.25
	0.0250	0.0125	0.02220	0.01143	17.10	17.02
1. NaBr 2. 0.322 mm	0.0500	0.0250	0.04250	0.02220	12.20	16.63
	0.0031	0.0015	0.00296	0.00146	17.60	18.10
	0.0062	0.0031	0.00583	0.00296	17.25	17.37
	0.0125	0.0062	0.01143	0.00583	17.20	17.25
1. NH ₄ Br 2. 0.298 mm	0.0250	0.0125	0.02220	0.01143	16.75	17.02
	0.0500	0.0250	0.04250	0.02220	10.00	16.62
	0.0031	0.0015	0.00296	0.00146	18.25	18.10
	0.0062	0.0031	0.00583	0.00296	17.30	17.37
1. NH ₄ I 2. 0.216 mm	0.0125	0.0062	0.01143	0.00583	17.25	17.25
	0.0250	0.0125	0.02220	0.01143	16.50	17.02
	0.0500	0.0250	0.04250	0.02220	16.00	16.63
	0.0031	0.0015	0.00296	0.00146	18.40	18.10
1. KI 2. 0.414 mm	0.0062	0.0031	0.00583	0.00296	17.25	17.37
	0.0125	0.0062	0.01143	0.00583	17.24	17.25
	0.0250	0.0125	0.02220	0.01143	17.00	17.02
	0.0500	0.0250	0.04250	0.02220	14.50	16.63
1. NH ₄ I 2. 0.216 mm	0.0031	0.0015	0.00296	0.00146	18.00	18.10
	0.0062	0.0031	0.00583	0.00296	17.50	17.37
	0.0125	0.0062	0.01143	0.00583	17.10	17.25
	0.0250	0.0125	0.02220	0.01143	17.25	17.02
1. KIO ₃ 2. 0.414 mm	0.0500	0.0250	0.04250	0.02220	16.90	16.83
	0.0031	0.0015	0.00297	0.00146	18.09	18.22
	0.0062	0.0031	0.00585	0.00297	17.15	17.39
	0.0125	0.0062	0.01147	0.00585	17.10	17.24
1. KNO ₃ 2. 0.355 mm	0.0250	0.0125	0.02240	0.01147	16.50	17.15
	0.0500	0.0250	0.04300	0.02240	12.20	16.72
	0.0031	0.0015	0.00296	0.00144	18.50	18.31
	0.0062	0.0031	0.00577	0.00296	17.50	17.14
1. NH ₄ NO ₃ 2. 0.412 mm	0.0125	0.0062	0.01120	0.00577	17.25	17.00
	0.0250	0.0125	0.02132	0.01122	16.50	16.45
	0.0500	0.0250	0.03850	0.02132	15.50	15.15
	0.0031	0.0015	0.00296	0.00144	18.33	18.31
1. K ₂ SO ₄ 2. 0.320 mm	0.0062	0.0031	0.00577	0.00296	17.50	17.14
	0.0125	0.0062	0.01120	0.00577	17.10	17.00
	0.0250	0.0125	0.02132	0.01122	16.75	17.45
	0.0500	0.0250	0.03850	0.02132	15.00	15.15
1. K ₂ SO ₄ 2. 0.320 mm	0.0015	0.00075	0.00121	0.00064	7.95	8.21
	0.0031	0.00150	0.00232	0.00121	7.90	8.29
	0.0062	0.00310	0.00414	0.00232	7.26	7.43
	0.0125	0.00620	0.00733	0.00414	7.10	7.30
	0.0250	0.01250	0.01255	0.00733	6.00	6.67

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DISCUSSION

As described in Part I¹, there is no influence of *pH* on the membrane potential in the case of film membranes of hemin, which though containing electrovalently bound negative Cl^- ion as well as replaceable H atoms, covalently bound in $-\text{COOH}$ group, does not behave as an ampholyte in the *pH* range 0.0 to 7.4. That electrovalently bound Cl^- ions in hemin film membrane could be completely exchanged with other monovalent or divalent negative radical is confirmed from the constancy of the membrane potentials. From Table I it appears that with Br^- , I^- , and IO_3^- ions, there is fairly a good agreement between the observed and the calculated values of the membrane potential within the molar range of concentrations of 0.0015 to 0.025*M* in the case of neutral aqueous solutions of KBr , NaBr , NH_4Br , KI , NaI , and KIO_3 , within an experimental error of $\pm 2.5\%$. In the case of Cl^- ion in various chlorides, the valid range was previously found to be 0.0015 to 0.05*M* by the author¹. In the case of NO_3^- ions, the valid range of concentration is 0.0015 to 0.05*M*, within experimental error of $\pm 2.5\%$ for the neutral aqueous solutions of NH_4NO_3 and KNO_3 ; in the case of SO_4^{2-} ions, the valid range of concentration is between 0.00075 and 0.0125*M* in the case of aqueous neutral solution of K_2SO_4 . The lower valid range of concentration in the case of SO_4^{2-} ions may be attributed to less ionisation of the sulphate of hematin.

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